

intervals. Fifteen plants of each cultivar were grown in insect-proof cages measuring 60 × 60 × 40 cm. Four plants were used for oviposition and four for nymphal hatching. Twenty 10-day-old *N. virescens* females were released in each cage, then removed after 24 hours. Four days later, half of the plants were dissected and eggs were counted under a microscope. Cultivars in the remaining cages were observed daily for 15 days and the emerging nymphs were counted.

Maximum temperature range was 27 to 37°C, minimum temperature ranged from 12 to 26°C, relative humidity varied from 60 to 87%, daily rainfall range was 0.0 to 15.5 mm, and sunshine varied from 3.4 to 9.9 hours.

Varietal preference for oviposition differed little. The number of eggs and nymphs per leafhopper was greater during monsoon season (July-October) than in winter (November-February) and summer (March-June) seasons (Table 1). Monthly data show there are oviposition/hatching peaks in September and March. The September peak was largest.

Table 1. Reproduction of *Nephotettix virescens* over 3 seasons on 3 rice varieties, Cuttack, India.

Season	Eggs (no./female)			Nymphs (no./female)		
	TN1	Jaya	IR20	TN1	Jaya	IR20
Winter (Nov-Feb)	4.1	3.4	4.1	2.0	2.0	2.5
Summer (Mar-Jun)	2.9	3.4	3.5	1.3	1.4	1.7
Monsoon (Jul-Oct)	7.1	6.9	7.4	3.1	3.0	3.2

Table 2. Relationship between meteorological factors and eggs and nymphs of *Nephotettix virescens*, Cuttack, India.^a

Meteorological factor	Correlation coefficients					
	Eggs			Nymphs		
	TN1	Jaya	IR20	TN1	Jaya	IR20
Relative humidity	0.5725**	0.5165**	0.5450**	0.5268**	0.4902*	0.2886
Rainfall	0.4753*	0.4173*	0.4805*	0.2455	0.2547	0.2979
Sunshine hours	-0.4922*	-0.4240*	-0.5137*	-0.2714	-0.2487	-0.2402

^a*Significant at P = 0.05, **significant at P = 0.01.

The number of eggs in all the cultivars was positively correlated with relative humidity and rainfall and negatively with hours of sunshine. Number of nymphs was positively correlated with relative humidity in Taichung Native 1 and Jaya (Table 2). This relationship indicates that relative humidity is more important in oviposition and nymphal

hatching. No temperature correlation was found.

Seasonal and monthly data indicated that optimum maximum temperature is 32°C, minimum temperature is 26°C. High relative humidity (84%), low intensity of rainfall, and limited sunshine hours (5.2 h) appeared to encourage oviposition and nymphal hatching. ✎

Life cycle of the green hairy caterpillar and its chemical control

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The green hairy caterpillar (*Noctuidae: Rivula nr. atimeta*) causes serious defoliation at the seedling stage of rice in the Philippines. Its life cycle was examined in artificial infestations in the greenhouse. Pairs of unequal size pupae were clipped to the tillers of 20day-old Taichung Native 1 (TN1) plants. The smaller of each pair was assumed to be male. Mylar cages kept emerging moths on the plants.

Female moths lay single eggs, an average of 128 each, or more than 16-224 per female. Eggs are laid in rows on both sides of a leaf, usually near the tip. The egg is round, 1 mm in diameter, and greenish when freshly laid. Incubation is 3-5 days.

Five larval instars last an average 13.5 days. A full-grown larva is 16 mm long with setae along the length of its body

Green hairy caterpillar (*Rivula nr. atimeta*).

(see figure). Pupation averages 5 days. Preoviposition is 14 days and oviposition averages 3.7 days. The life span is 4.1 days for males, 5.2 days for females.

Nine insecticides were evaluated against the green hairy caterpillar. To determine contact toxicity, compounds were sprayed on third-instar larvae in

petri dishes using a Potter's spray tower. After spraying, the larvae were transferred to untreated TN1 leaves in petri dishes.

To determine foliar toxicity, 25 ml insecticide solution was sprayed on 30-day-old plants using a bottle atomizer. Treated leaves were cut, placed in petri dishes, and infested with 10 third-instar larvae each.

Monocrotophos, diazinon, and azinphos ethyl were effective as both contact and foliar sprays (see table). Brodan, carbofuran, and methyl parathion were effective as foliar sprays.

Effect of selected insecticides on control of hairy caterpillar, 48 hours after treatment, at IRRI.

Insecticide ^a	Mortality ^b (%)	
	Contact spray	Foliar spray
Monocrotophos 16.8 EC	100.0 a	100.0 a
Diazinon 20 EC	100.0 a	100.0 a
Azinphos ethyl 40 EC	100.0 a	100.0 a
Carbofuran 20 F	32.5 b	95.0 a
Brodan (20% chlorpyrifos + 10.5% BPMC) EC	42.5 b	100.0 a
Methyl parathion 50 EC	7.5 c	82.5 a
Metalkamate 30 EC	2.5 c	0.0 c
Ethylan 45 EC	0.0 c	30.0 b
Mipcin 50 WP	0.0 c	0.0 c
Control (untreated)	0.0 c	0.0 c

^aAt 0.04% solution. ^bAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Chemical control of azolla insects

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Insect damage is the most important limiting factor in production of azolla as a supplementary nitrogen source for rice cultivation in Thailand. Two insecticide trials were conducted on azolla at Bangkok Rice Experiment Station in 1980. The first experiment examined plant soaking in a 0.01% concentration of insecticide for 10 minutes before field inoculation and postinoculation sprays. The second compared 7 insecticides including *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bactospine) applied after field inoculation. Both experiments involved 3- × 5-m² plots in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications.

Webworm *Cryptoblabes* sp. and

caseworm *Nymphula enixalis* were the major insect pests. Azolla was damaged by insects and high temperatures during April, and by competition with blue-green algae. Monocrotophos spray gave the best insect control and highest yield (Table 1). Monocrotophos plant soak was moderately effective within 10 days

after azolla release into the field. Carbaryl was ineffective. Broadcast carbofuran provided poor insect control and azolla development. Results of the second trial confirmed that monocrotophos was the most effective insecticide among those tested for controlling defoliating insects (Table 2). Carbosulfan

Table 2. Effect of foliar insecticides sprayed on azolla insect pests at Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Bangkok, Thailand, August 1980.

Treatment ^a	Insect infestation ^b (grade)		Fresh weight ^c (t/ha)
	10 DI	17 DI	
Monocrotophos 56% WSC	0	0	23.8 a
Carbosulfan 20% EC	++	0	21.5 ab
Chlorpyrifos 20% EC	++	0	21.0 ab
Malathion 83% EC	+++	+	17.2 abc
Fenitrothion 86% EC	++	0	15.0 bc
Bactospeine 16,000/mg	++	++	14.9 bc
Dimethoate 40% EC	++	+++	11.0 cd
Untreated control	++	+++	7.4 d

^aInsecticides were applied 1 and 10 days after field inoculation at 0.3 kg ai/ha. Bactospeine was used at 1 kg formulated product/ha. ^bIncidences of webworm and caseworm were estimated at 10 and 17 days after inoculation: 0 = no damage, + = light, ++ = moderate, +++ = severe. DI = days after inoculation. ^cMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$).

Table 1. Effect of insecticide treatments on insects and azolla development at Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Bangkok, Thailand, April 1980.^a

Treatment ^b	10 days		20 days	
	Azolla development (%)	Insect infestation	Azolla development (%)	Insect infestation
Monocrotophos spray at 1 and 10 days	70 a	0	75 a	0
Monocrotophos dip before planting	38 bc	+	0 c	+++
Monocrotophos dip and spray at 10 days	45 b	+	43 ab	++
Carbaryl spray at 1 and 10 days	23 c	++	13 bc	+++
Carbaryl dip before planting	25 c	++	0 c	+++
Carbaryl dip and spray at 10 days	23 c	++	27 bc	+++
Carbofuran broadcast at 1 and 10 days	20 c	++	0 c	+++
Untreated control	25 c	++	0 c	+++

^aAzolla development was estimated by surface area covered by azolla. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($p = 0.05$). Insect infestation scale: 0 = no damage, + = light, ++ = moderate, +++ = severe. ^bFoliar insecticides were sprayed at 0.5 kg ai/ha, 0.01% of insecticide solution was used for dipping, and carbofuran was applied at 1 kg ai/ha.